

WARNING: this list will not be anymore updated after this version

LIST OF THE CMIP6-DRIVEN HISTORICAL AND SCENARIO RUNS OF THE MED-CORDEX BASELINE RUNS

version 0: S. Somot, January 2022

version 1: S. Somot, April 2022, update after the Med-CORDEX workshop in Baseline runs

version 2: S. Somot, 26 Sept 2022, first official list, posted on zenodo

version 3: S. Somot, 12 mai 2023, various changes in preparation of the Med-CORDEX workshop

version 4: S. Somot, 1 Aug 2023, changes with the info from Med-CORDEX workshop, posted on zenodo

Version 5: S. Somot, 13 June 2024, changes after the Med-CORDEX workshop, posted on zenodo

Version 6: S. Somot, 20 April 2026, we stop using this list from now on to only rely on the official CORDEX simulation list,

<https://wcrp-cordex.github.io/simulation-status/>

In Med-CORDEX, 5 scenario runs have been performed with 3 different RCSM configurations and by 3 different institutes. 3 different CMIP6 GCMs and 1 different SSP scenarios are covered.

Color Code: **Simulations done**, **Simulations in preparation**

Model, <i>source_id</i>	Driving GCM	Scenario	Period	Status	<i>Last update</i>
CNRM-RCSM6-SN	CNRM-ESM2-1, r1i1p1f2	SSP585	1980-2100	done	2023-04
CNRM-RCSM6B-SN	NorESM2-MM, r1i1p1f1	SSP585	1960-2100	done	2026-04
CNRM-RCSM6B-SN	NorESM2-MM, r1i1p1f1	SSP370	1960-2100	done	2026-04
CNRM-RCSM6B-SN	NorESM2-MM, r1i1p1f1	SSP126	1960-2100	planned	2026-04
CNRM-RCSM6B-SN	One more GCM to be chosen	SSP370	1960-2100	planned	2026-04
ENEA-REG2	MPI-ESM1-2-HR r1i1p1f1	SSP585	1981-2100	done	2023-05

ENEA-REG2	MPI-ESM1-2-HR r1i1p1f1	SSP245	1981-2100	done	2023-05
ENEA-REG2	MPI-ESM1-2-HR r1i1p1f1	SSP126	1981-2100	done	2023-05
ENEA-REG3	MPI-ESM1-2-HR r1i1p1f1	SSP370	1960-2100	running	2026-04
ENEA-REG3	EC-Earth3, r1i1p1f1	SSP370	1960-2100	running	2024-04
CCLM5-0-9-NEMOMED12-3-6	EC-Earth3-Veg, r12i1p1f1	SSP585	1950-2100	done	2023-04
RegCM-ES1-1	possible contribution with one or more GCMs among MPI-ESM1-2-HR, CNRM-ESM2-1, NorESM2-MM, EC-Earth3-Veg,	SSP370		planned	2025-07
RegCM-ES1-1	Same as above	SSP126		planned	2025-03
RegIPSLv2	IPSL-CM6A-LR	To be decided		planned	2023-05
LMDZ4-NEMOMED8v2				planned	2024-05
MedESM				planned	2024-05
ICON-OASIS-NEMO	MPI-ESM1-2-HR, r1i1p1f1	SSP370		planned	2024-05
MedX-CM				planned	2025-06

REFERENCES: